

**Most Effective behavioral
interventions in
increasing household recycling participation**
A Rapid Review

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Introduction

Part B of this White Paper builds on the evidence-based analysis conducted in Part A by addressing a key knowledge gap within the National Waste Policy 2018 – Less Waste, More Resources (Commonwealth of Australia, 2018). This gap concerns the limited integration of behavioural evidence into household recycling initiatives under Australia’s circular economy agenda. While the policy articulates ambitious circular economy goals, it provides limited empirical evidence on how behavioural change can enhance household participation in recycling programs. This paper will argue that understanding these behavioural mechanisms is critical for designing scalable interventions aligned with Australia’s resource recovery and emissions reduction targets. A rapid review was therefore selected to balance rigour and timeliness for near-term policy application.

To strengthen this evidence base, Part B undertakes a Rapid review to synthesise current knowledge on behavioural interventions that motivate communities to recycle more effectively. Given the policy urgency and the need for timely insights, this approach enables the efficient synthesis of available evidence to inform near-term policy actions (de Costa et al., 2025). The review follows a structured, transparent Population–Intervention–Comparison–Outcome (PICO) framework addressing the question:

“What behavioural interventions are most effective in increasing household recycling participation?”

This question directly responds to evidence needs identified in the National Waste Policy 2018. Here, Population = Australian households; Intervention = behavioural tools such as incentives or social-norm programs; Comparison = baseline or alternative approaches; Outcome = increased recycling participation and reduced waste.

Background and Rationale

In 2018–19, Australia generated about 76 million tonnes of waste, with households contributing 12.4 million tonnes (ABS, 2020). Household waste mainly includes food, plastics, and e-waste; food waste alone represents 35–45% of household residual waste. Of this, roughly 91% ends up in landfills, and only 9% is recycled (Edwards et al., 2018). This highlights a substantial behavioural gap requiring targeted interventions to improve waste separation and participation in recycling programs.

A circular economy keeps materials in use through reuse, repair, and recycling, creating a closed-loop system that minimises waste (Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and

Water, 2024). In this context, household behaviour is pivotal to achieving circular economy goals; However, the National Waste Policy 2018 offers limited guidance on influencing consumer behaviour through evidence-based strategies (Commonwealth of Australia, 2018).

Behavioural interventions refer to the application of psychological and social science principles, such as feedback, commitment, and social norms, to encourage desired actions and discourage environmentally harmful behaviours (Ajzen, 1991). Linking behavioural theory to policy design clarifies how individual choices can drive systemic waste outcomes. Globally, interventions such as community education, financial incentives, feedback systems, and social norm messaging have demonstrated potential to increase recycling participation; however, their comparative effectiveness and contextual suitability for Australia remain underexplored.

Understanding effective approaches is vital for creating practical and equitable solutions that meet policy goals, reducing waste and improving resource recovery. This review analyses existing evidence to provide actionable insights for policymakers and local governments on enhancing recycling participation and community engagement. The findings aim to connect policy objectives with everyday behavior, aiding Australia's transition to a circular, low-waste economy.

Review Protocol

This study employed a rapid review methodology guided by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework. As highlighted by Devane et al. (2024), rapid reviews are increasingly used in policy contexts because they balance timeliness with methodological rigour, applying justified shortcuts while maintaining transparency and replicability. This review focused on peer-reviewed primary research articles and proceeded through four key steps: literature search, screening, data extraction, and quality assessment. Each step of the protocol was designed to isolate behavioural interventions relevant to households.

Search Strategy

A Boolean search string was developed using the PICO framework to align with the research question (Table 1). Searches were conducted across ProQuest, Scopus, and Web of Science to ensure interdisciplinary coverage spanning behavioural science, environmental engineering, and policy research. ProQuest provided access to behavioural and social policy studies, Scopus to sustainability and environmental journals, and Web of Science to citation-indexed high-quality publications, thereby maximising comprehensiveness and reliability.

PICO Element	Description	Boolean Combination
P (Population)	Households engaging in recycling activities	("household recycling participation" OR "recycling behaviour" OR "waste sorting" OR "community recycling") AND "Australia"
I (Intervention)	Behavioural interventions designed to increase recycling	("behavioural intervention*" OR "behavioural strategy" OR "nudge" OR "education campaign" OR "social norm*")
C (Comparison)	Other or no intervention/ traditional waste management practices	("no intervention" OR "control condition")
O (Outcome)	Increase in household recycling participation or rates	("recycling participation" OR "waste reduction" OR "recycling rate" OR "behaviour change")
Final Combined Search String		("behavioural intervention*" OR "nudge" OR "education campaign") AND ("household recycling" OR "recycling behaviour" OR "waste sorting") AND "Australia" AND ("no intervention").

Table 1: search terms aligned with the elements of RQ (PICO framework)

Screening and Eligibility Process

Considering the eligibility process through databases, 86 studies were found.

	Location	Language	Year	Population	Intervention	Source Type
Inclusion	Australia	English	2015-2025	households	behavioural interventions	Primary sources
Exclusions	Non-Australian	non-English	prior to 2015	industrial or commercial	Non-behavioural interventions	Secondary sources/grey literature

Table 2: Eligibility Criteria

All records were imported into EndNote 20 for deduplication and organised screening. Then, they were screened by title and abstract against predefined criteria in Table 1 (first screen) and the second screen was conducted through full-text screening. The PRISMA flow chart (Figure 1) illustrates the number of articles included and excluded at each stage of the review. Screening was completed by a single reviewer under time constraints, with all decisions transparently documented. Figure 1 presents the data screening process following the PRISMA flow chart framework.

Figure 1. PRISMA flow chart illustrating the screening process and number of articles included/excluded.

Data Extraction and Quality Assessment

Key data fields—study identification, design, population, and intervention type—were extracted into a structured collation table (Appendix 2). The quality of studies was assessed using a traffic light system for its clarity and rapid interpretability. Each study was rated for relevance, sampling representativeness, measurement validity, analytical transparency, Bias control and quality of the paper (Appendix 1). Potential bias was mitigated through transparent documentation, triangulation across multiple databases, and alignment with PRISMA standards, thereby preserving validity and replicability. The documented protocol allows future researchers to reproduce this review process.

Results

Key Findings

As shown in Figure 1, 86 studies identified and 11 peer-reviewed studies were included in this review (Appendix 2). All directly addressed the PICO research question by comparing behavioural interventions to identify those most effective in increasing household recycling participation. None examined all eight intervention categories; instead, the number of interventions compared within individual studies ranged from two to six. Across the included studies, several recurring patterns emerged:

- **Convenience and accessibility** were the most consistent predictors of recycling behaviour. The introduction of kitchen caddies, clear bin labelling, and accessible drop-off or container-refund points significantly improved participation rates in urban areas (O'Dwyer et al., 2022; Bernardo et al., 2023).
- **Financial incentives**, such as deposit refund, generated rapid short-term engagement but plateaued when logistical barriers persisted, indicating their effectiveness depends on pairing with structural convenience (O'Dwyer et al., 2022; Phipps et al., 2024).
- **Social-norm and identity-based approaches** fostered longer-term commitment by framing recycling as a socially valued norm (Varotto & Spagnolli, 2017; Nguyen et al., 2022).
- **Information, feedback, and awareness mechanisms** enhanced self-efficacy and routine maintenance when personalised (Landells et al., 2022; Keegan & Breadsell, 2021).
- **Governance factors**, such as municipal coordination and consistency across local councils, amplified program success by reducing confusion and building public trust (Bernardo et al., 2023; Ananda et al., 2023).

Barriers reported across studies included limited recycling infrastructure in multi-unit dwellings (Nguyen et al., 2022), low trust in recycling outcomes (O'Dwyer et al., 2022), fragmented governance and inconsistent messaging (Bernardo et al., 2023), and a lack of targeted education for culturally diverse communities (Keegan & Breadsell, 2021). Overall, interventions combining convenience, social norms, and feedback mechanisms achieved the most sustained improvements.

Quality of Evidence

As detailed in Appendix 1, quality was assessed using a traffic-light system, with six articles rated green and five yellow, indicating strong methodological transparency and minimal bias. Most

employed cross-sectional designs with clear outcome measures; however, population heterogeneity limited direct comparison. The focus on urban Australian contexts enhances policy relevance but reduces generalisability to remote regions.

Limitations of the Rapid Review

This rapid review adopted several shortcuts that may introduce bias:

1. Language restriction: potential language bias
2. Date-limited scope: exclusion of older studies
3. Database restriction: publication bias
4. Exclusion of grey literature – omission of practical insights
5. Single-reviewer screening and extraction – higher risk of selection and recording bias
6. Condensed quality appraisal – reduced scrutiny
7. Narrative synthesis without meta-analysis – limited quantitative comparability
8. Time-bounded search (no backward citation tracking) – possible omission of relevant evidence

These limitations favoured more recent and English-language studies, potentially under-representing practical program evaluations. The single-reviewer process may have introduced a subjective element in the selection. Despite these constraints, the protocol remained transparent and replicable, supporting confidence that multi-component behavioural interventions most effectively enhance household recycling participation in the Australian context.

Conclusion

This rapid review synthesised current evidence on behavioural interventions that enhance household recycling participation in Australia. The analysis identified convenience, feedback, and social-norm mechanisms as the most effective drivers of sustained behavioural change. However, evidence gaps—particularly in rural contexts, longitudinal assessment, and demographic diversity—limit generalisability. To advance Australia’s circular economy goals, future iterations of the National Waste Policy should embed behavioural insights into program design, integrating multi-component, community-centred approaches supported by transparent governance and performance feedback. Future research should also strengthen methodological rigour through dual screening, inclusion of grey literature, and meta-analysis to improve comparability and policy relevance.

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AI Declaration

In preparing this essay, I used generative AI tools, specifically ChatGPT and Grammarly, to enhance my APA 7th referencing, improve grammar, and clarify my expression. However, all critical arguments, analyses, and selections of sources are my own work. The AI tools were used solely for support in presentation and referencing, not for content generation or evidence fabrication.

Appendix 1
Quality assessment table

Scoring Scheme for Quality:		No.	Lead Author Name	Study Quality						
				Sampling representativeness	Data validity	Analysis transparency	Bias control	Relevance to RQ	Overall Score	Traffic light
1 = Yes, 0.5 = Partial, 0 = No across										
5 domains:		1	Islam et al.	0.5	0.5	1	0.5	1	3.5	
1. Sampling representativeness		2	Xu, Wheeler, & Tchatoka	1	1	1	1	1	5	
2. Measurement validity/reliability		3	Landells et al.	0.5	1	1	1	1	4.5	
3. Analytical transparency		4	O'Dwyer et al.	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	1	3	
4. Bias control		5	Varotto & Spagnolli	1	1	1	1	1	5	
5. Relevance to research question		6	Keegan & Breadsell	0.5	0.5	1	0.5	1	3.5	
		7	Nguyen et al.	1	1	1	1	1	5	
Sum scores	Colour	8	Bernardo et al.	0.5	0.5	1	0.5	1	3.5	
4.0–5.0	Green	9	Landells et al.	0.5	0.5	1	0.5	1	3.5	
2.5–3.9	Yellow	10	Ananda et al.	1	1	1	1	1	5	
< 2.5	Red	11	Phipps et al.	0.5	1	1	0.5	1	4	

Appendix 2

Collation table

(Note: For better readability, this table has been divided across two pages.)

No.	Lead Author Name	Year Published	Study Design	Sample & Population
1	Islam et al.	2022	Quantitative	Australian residents, Sydney metropolitan area (n = 400) recruited nationwide; survey of adults aged 18+.
2	Xu, Wheeler, & Tchatoaka	2023	Quantitative	8 South Australian councils, monthly panel data (2006–2020), analyzing municipal waste diversion performance.
3	Landells et al.	2025	Qualitative	Australian local government waste managers, a national survey (n = 183) and online interviews (n = 45) across multiple states.
4	O'Dwyer et al.	2022	Quantitative	Perth residents / households n ≈ 400 respondents (across metropolitan areas).
5	Varotto & Spagnolli	2017	Synthesis	Global household samples 36 independent field studies (≈40,000 households) on behavioral recycling interventions across multiple countries (70 intervention datasets).
6	Keegan & Breadsell	2021	Qualitative	Australian households (case-based sample of 75 households); qualitative participants recruited for interviews and observations (two-week diaries + follow-up survey).
7	Nguyen et al.	2022	Quantitative	Australian households (n = 1027); respondents from multiple regions across Australia.
8	Bernardo et al.	2023	Quantitative	Households within Wollongong LGA Municipal data (no direct survey).
9	Landells et al.	2022	Qualitative	Australian local councils and communities involved in organics waste treatment programs; qualitative case-based participants.
10	Ananda et al.	2023	Quantitative	Australian households n = 4,324 national respondents (via online panel).
11	Phipps et al.	2024	Quantitative	Queensland residents (age 18 +, pre/post CDS launch) Baseline n = 199; final n = 90 participants (41.5 ± 13.8 yrs; 77 male, 13 female). Data collected Jan 2018 → Feb 2019 via online Qualtrics survey.

No.	Lead Author Name	Category of Intervention							
		Monetary or Economic Incentives	Convenience, Prompts & Accessibility	Information, Feedback & Awareness	Commitment, Norms & Identity-Based Interventions	Habit Formation & Routine Reinforcement	Upskilling & Competence / Practice-Based Change	Environmental / Contextual Design Changes	Governance, Leadership & Policy Supports
1	Islam et al.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unsure	No	No	Yes	No
2	Xu, Wheeler, & Tchatoka	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
3	Landells et al.	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	Unsure	No	Yes
4	O'Dwyer et al.	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
5	Varotto & Spagnolli	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
6	Keegan & Breadsell	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
7	Nguyen et al.	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
8	Bernardo et al.	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No
9	Landells et al.	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
10	Ananda et al.	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
11	Phipps et al.	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No